

10 essential steps to writing an engaging project description that attracts volunteers

The CS Track team members Dr. Yaela Golumbic (The Mofet institute; The Steinhardt Museum of Natural History, Israel) and Marius Oesterheld (Wissenschaft im Dialog, Germany) have recently published a ten-step **guide to writing citizen science project descriptions** that spark interest and attract volunteers.

Over the past 18 months, several research groups within the CS Track consortium have analysed project descriptions stored in the CS Track database from different perspectives (focusing for instance on research area, correlation with the SDG framework, educational aspects etc.). What has become apparent in the course of this work is that CS project descriptions are extremely heterogeneous – both in terms of format, length, and style, and regarding their content. In the proposed template, Yaela and Marius present some of what we have learnt during the process and offer a set of recommendations for writing engaging project descriptions.

In addition to providing general advice on length, style and presentation, this template guides the reader through the process of writing a project description in ten simple steps. These ten steps are explained in very concrete terms and illustrated with text examples. The annotated template is available as a PDF download on the CS Track Zenodo page [here](#).

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